

Addendum

Adapted Work Programme

Second funding phase

Decided by the Steering committee in February 2026

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Introduction

About

This document outlines the adaptations made to the NFDI4Biodiversity work programme compared to the renewal proposal for the second funding phase. These adaptations were decided by the Steering committee after the approved funding was approximately 30 percent less than the amount originally requested.

Strategies

The Task Areas and Measures had the following strategies available to reduce workload in response to the budget cuts:

- Each Task Area has 2-3 milestones - check if they can be downsized.
- Each Measure has an objective and activities towards this objective - check if activities can be (visibly) reduced.
- Each Measure is required to pledge committed results for each calendar year - if possible, indicate on Measure level how planned annual output and progress can be adapted (i.e., spread out or reduced).
- It is also possible to drop or merge Measures.

Document structure

The subsequent chapters outline for each Task Area the main changes made to Milestones, Measures, activities, and resources. Deletions compared to the original renewal proposal are marked in **red** or **crossed-out-in-red**, other changes or additions are formatted in **blue**. The following table provides an overview of the deletion or consolidation of Measures.

Overview of Task Areas and associated Measures <u>after</u> application of budget cuts		
Task Area	Measures	Responsible Co-spokesperson(s)
TA1: Community enabling and support (2enable)	(1) Community-driven topic tables (2) Novel data pipelines (3) Open species occurrence data (4) Training and education (5) User support (6) Legal aspects	Aletta Bonn Birgit Gemeinholzer Ortrun Brand
TA2: International networking and standards (2connect)	(1) Norm vocabularies and data annotation (2) International involvement and cooperation (3) Standards	Anton Güntsch Uwe Scholz

Overview of Task Areas and associated Measures <u>after</u> application of budget cuts		
Task Area	Measures	Responsible Co-spokesperson(s)
TA3: A sustainable service and data network (2consolidate)	(1) Service portfolio, lifecycle and quality (2) Strengthening local research data management (3) Enhancing the network of the national GFBio data centers (4) Service portfolio and lifecycle (merged with TA3 M1)	Birgitta König-Ries Stefan Seifert
TA4: Research Data Commons (2create)	(1) Data products (2) Data and service integration (3) Platform (4) Governance	Ivaylo Kostadinov Philipp Wieder
TA5: Coordination, collaborative governance and sustainability (2coordinate)	(1) Project office (2) Communications office (3) Integration with NFDI and sustainability	Frank Oliver Glöckner Barbara Ebert Jörg Overmann Jens Stoye

Task Area 1

Community enabling and support (2enable)

Lead: UJena, Co-Lead: UKassel, UMR

Milestones for Task Area 1 - Milestone 1.2 adapted

Measuring progress towards SA1 (the specific aim of the Task Area): "Subcommunities have tailored solutions for their research needs"

MTA	Project month	Milestone	Means of verification
1.1	24	A consolidated service concept for research support pipelines, together with other local helpdesks and with other NFDI consortia, has been established.	Concept for expert support consolidated, verified and published, including resources for long-term operation
1.2	30	The consortium offers robust workflows for the formation of domain teams who experience reports about the topic table concept, including the domain teams concept, to solve specific problems or develop research-ready data products.	Concepts and workflows for end-user related domain-specific RDM subcommunities are consolidated and published
2.3	48	A joint & tested training service concept, together with other suitable NFDI-Consortia, is established.	Peer-reviewed paper describing the training and service concept, shaping the ground for decisions on a common Data Academy

TA1 Measure 1: Topic tables

Lead: UKassel, Co-Lead: UJena

Contributors: All partners

Activity 1 - Topic table instalment: **no changes**

Activity 2 - Development of concepts and workflows: **no changes**

Activity 3 - Support generation of outputs: **no changes**

Staff concept and resources: The work planned in Measure 1 will require a Scientific Data Steward (1 FTE) with good project management, coordination and self-organisation skills, excellent communication skills and in-depth knowledge of [NFDI4Biodiversity processes, services and expertise](#), as well as the biodiversity community and its stakeholders.

TA1 Measure 2: Novel data pipelines

Lead: UKassel, **Co-Lead:** UJena

Contributors: UFZ, UDE, BGBM, LIB

Activity 1 - Metabarcoding: **no changes**

Activity 2 - Lab tools for ecology: **no changes**

Activity 3 - Data streams: **no changes**

Staff concept and resources: The work planned for this task will require computational and coordination skills to bridge the gap between researchers and software developers and test and evaluate available tools and features dependent on the respective biodiversity subcommunities and their demands. For this purpose, 2x 0.5 FTE (coordinator & data scientist) at UKassel and ~~0.3 FTE~~ 0.12 FTE (data scientist) at UFZ are allocated (~~adding up to a full-time position with capacities in Task Areas 3 and 4~~). We're facing a challenge with reduced funding, but we're committed to making it work and will be relying on our existing personnel to deliver our work program and meet our milestones.

TA1 Measure 3: Open occurrence data

Lead: UJena, **Co-Leads:** BGBM, UJena

Contributors: IFL, iDiv, GFBio Data Centers, GDA, Gfl, GdO, DDA, AraGes, NetPhyD, NABU/Naturgucker, BfN-NMZB, UBA, LAU, HLNUG, SenMVKU, NLWKN

Activity 1 - Mobilising and harmonising data: **no changes**

Activity 2 - Co-developing the Living Atlas Portal: **additional funds required**

Activity 3 - Community engagement for the Living Atlas Portal: **no changes**

Activity 4 - Putting data to use: **pilot**

Staff concept and resources: To enable a strong community network a 0.5 FTE coordinator will be hired at UJena-BIO, responsible for strategy development, coordination and networking across stakeholders. For data mobilising, curation and harmonising ~~a 0.5 FTE data steward, and~~ a 0.5 FTE data scientist will be employed (~~both~~ UJena-BIO). To ensure smooth data delivery pipelines with various data providers a 0.5 FTE service steward ~~and~~ ~~0.9 FTE software development capacities to co-develop functionalities are~~ is planned at BGBM ~~and UJena-INF~~. ~~To foster innovative data visualisation to ensure an immersive, attractive and fascinating NFDI4Biodiversity and Living Atlas experience, a 0.5 FTE designer will be employed (IFL), who will also facilitate visualisations for domain teams in the topic tables.~~

TA1 Measure 4: Education and training

Lead: UMR, **Co-Leads:** GFBio

Contributors: ~~UGOE-CIDAS~~; ZMT, FBN, IOW, NMZB, IÖR, UBA, involved federal state initiatives, UJena

Activity 1 - Custom RDM training: **no changes**

Activity 2 - Seasonal schools: **no changes**

Activity 3 - Trainings on tools and services: **no changes**

Activity 4 - Open educational resources: **no changes**

Activity 5 - Train-the-trainer network: **no changes**

Staff concept and resources: To coordinate activities and expand the Training and education offers of NFDI4Biodiversity as a broad, domain-specific and - at the same time - general service, 1 FTE for a service steward is needed (UMR). To ensure reverse distribution and information across other task Areas and into the NFDI, a service steward position at GFBio will contribute capacities of 0.5 FTE. Further resources or organisation, teaching and documentation of events will be made available by partners. An annual budget of ~~15,000~~ **5,000** EUR is calculated for direct costs of events and training materials.

TA1 Measure 5: User support

Lead: UniBremen-MARUM, **Co-Leads:** GFBio, FBN

Contributors: GFBio Data Centers (BGBM, DSMZ, IPK, ENA, LIB, MfN, UniBremen-MARUM, AWI, SGN, SMNS, SNSB), Service Providers (GFBio, UFZ, GWDG, UJena, AWI, InfAI, JLU, BIBI, UMR, HITS), RDM networks (UMR, ZMT, IOW, UBA, UFZ, UGOE, ~~Thünen~~, IfL, BioFID, involved federal state initiatives)

Activity 1 - Back office: **no changes**

Activity 2 - Extended expert network: **no changes**

Activity 3 - Fostering knowledge transfer: **reduce activities**

Activity 4 - User satisfaction: **no changes**

Activity 5 - Dispatching: **no changes**

Staff concept and resources: **Staff resources are reduced from 0.5 FTE to 0.4 FTE** for a coordinator at UniBremen-MARUM for management, strategy development, and quality assurance. This will be complemented by ~~0.5 FTE~~ **0.4 FTE** for cross-community coordination (including the biodata interest group) in Task Area 5 Measure 3. The first level support team will remain stable to meet user requests in the second funding phase (0.5 FTE for Data Stewards at GFBio and ~~0.5 FTE~~ **0.4 FTE** for Data Stewards at PANGAEA) to support with

data mobilisations, documentation, communication, and knowledge management. In sum:
Reduced outreach and dissemination activities (talks, workshops etc.) due to budget cuts.
Reduced capacities: 0.4 instead of 0.5 FTE for management/strategic development; and 0.4
instead of 0.5 FTE for the Data Steward at PANGAEA.

Deleted: TA1 Measure 6: Legal aspects

Lead: UMR

Contributors: UFU, BfN-NMZB, FBN, ZMT

~~Activity 1 – Information material~~

~~Activity 2 – Practical support~~

~~Activity 3 – Good practice~~

~~Activity 4 – Templates~~

~~Activity 5 – Data policies~~

Task Area 2

International networking and standards (2connect)

Lead: BGBM, **Co-Lead:** IPK

Task Area 2 had only very limited resources available for the implementation of the work programme for each of the three measures even before the budget cuts, with a total of only 1 FTE per Measure. Therefore, if individual activities and milestones would have been deleted, a reduction of resources across all measures would have jeopardised the ability to carry out the work. TA2 therefore decided to implement the radical removal of Measure 3 (Standards) as proposed by the coordination team (see details below); this also implied the removal of Milestone 2.3, which had been addressed by Measure 3. Beyond this radical cut, the IPK has offered to cover the 0.5 FTE allocated to IPK in Measure 2 from other de.NBI/ELIXIR-DE activities financed until the end of 2027, if necessary. The savings contribution of TA2 would thus be up to 50%.

Milestones for Task Area 2 - *Milestone 2.3 deleted (together with Measure 3)*

Measuring progress towards SA2 (the specific aim of the Task Area): "Embedment in the international data and service provider community"

MTA	Project month	Milestone	Means of verification
2.1	24	International working group of national biodiversity data infrastructures formed and coordinated by NFDI4Biodiversity.	Public working group charter
2.2	26	Workflow for the annotation of taxonomic research data documented, tested and established in various data centers.	Workflow published
2.3	48	Bioschemas implementations, RDC interfaces and cross-NFDI query mechanisms up and running and documented.	Service specifications published

TA2 Measure 1: Norm vocabularies and data annotation

Lead: BGBM, **Co-Lead:** LIB

Contributors: InfAI (BiodivPortal), DSMZ (LPSN), SNSB (DTN Service), DLR-RLZ, GWDG

Activity 1 - (Taxonomic) data annotation: **no changes**

Activity 2 - Connecting special taxon lists: **no changes**

Activity 3 - Handling standard vocabularies: **no changes**

Staff concept and resources: Implementing the measure requires a sound knowledge of standards and service based workflows. Scientific data curators will be responsible for the specification of annotation workflows and their implementation (0.5 FTE at BGBM, 0.25 FTE at LIB). ~~Software developer capacities are necessary to provide efficient~~ Reuse of TS4NFDI search widgets which will be required at data center level for terminologies of the BiodivPortal (~~0.25 FTE at InfAI~~ will be supported in TA4).

TA2 Measure 2: Cooperation with international biodiversity informatics infrastructures

Lead: BGBM, **Co-Lead**: IPK

Contributors: GFBio, DSMZ, iDiv, SNSB

Activity 1 - Collaboration with target infrastructures: **no changes**

Activity 2 - Cooperation agreements for external services: **no changes**

Activity 3 - Cooperation with molecular data repositories: **no changes**

Activity 4 - International working group coordination: **no changes**

Staff concept and resources: The measure requires a thorough understanding of the relevant international initiatives and standards as well as good communication. Tasks include the identification and coordination of integration of target services as well as the involvement of the biodiversity informatics community as well as national data infrastructures worldwide. For this, 0.5 FTE ~~each~~ at BGBM (covering biodiversity informatics) ~~and IPK (covering bioinformatics)~~ for scientific data curators are planned.

Deleted: TA2 Measure 3: Standards

~~**Lead**: MARUM, **Co-Lead**: BGBM~~

~~**Contributors**: AWI, DSMZ, RPTU, InfAI, all GFBio Data Centers~~

~~Activity 1—Enhance the discoverability and usability~~

~~Activity 2—Knowledge graph technologies~~

~~Activity 3—Cross-community harmonisation~~

~~Activity 4—Standards-related expertise~~

Measure 3 had to be deleted due to the budget cuts. The main considerations were:

- The removal of the measure reduces the TA budget by one third.

- Work on the development of bioschemas would be continued on a reduced scale by the data centres that consider themselves capable of doing so.
- An accompanying DFG proposal on the topic of bioschema could be developed.
- Other standardisation issues would need to be addressed (as far as possible) in TA2 M2, TA3 and TA4.

Task Area 3

A sustainable service and data network (2consolidate)

Lead: UJena, **Co-Leads:** SNSB

Task Area 3 deals with the budget cuts in several ways. Most significantly, TA3 M4 (Service portfolio and lifecycle) was deleted as a separate Measure and merged with TA3 M1, which, in return, was renamed into Service portfolio, lifecycle and quality. Moreover, the planned achievement of Milestone 3.1 has been postponed by six months, from project month 18 to month 24.

Milestones for Task Area 3 - *Milestone 3.1 postponed by 6 months*

Measuring progress towards SA3 (the specific aim of the Task Area): “A consolidated, community-owned service portfolio”

MTA	Project month	Milestone	Means of verification
3.1	18 24	Established support for service providers towards professionalisation	Formalised action plan published
3.2	30	Assessment of the Service Catalog and Service Portfolio Management	Service Portfolio Report published
3.3	36	Comprehensive support and tool pool for local data management	Guide published as a living document; helpdesk is competent with ELNs; biodiversity data manager network established
3.4	48	Agreed model for scientific data trustee organisations in biology	Position paper published

TA3 Measure 1: ~~Service quality and development~~ Service portfolio, lifecycle and quality

Merged with TA3 Measure 4: Service portfolio and lifecycle (~~TA3 M4 deleted~~)

Lead: GWDG, **Co-Lead:** GFBio, IPK

Activity 1 – Portfolio management (new activity, added from deleted TA3 M4)

Activity 2 – Service Quality Awareness & Assurance

Activity 3 – Sustainability Assessment

Activity 4 – Service Promotion

Staff concept and resources: The measure requires staff with good knowledge of the service landscape in NFDI4Biodiversity, the biodiversity domain and the NFDI. It will be equipped with 2x 0.5 FTE for coordination, a part-time service steward and a part-time software developer located at the lead and co-lead institutions GWDG and IPK respectively.

TA3 Measure 2: Local research data management

Lead: UJena, **Co-Leads:** GFBio, SNSB

Contributors: H-ITS, UFZ, RPTU

Activity 1 - Enhance Workbenches and tools: **reduced number of tools**

Activity 2 - Early Data Management Guide: **no changes**

Activity 3 - Support and hosting: **no changes**

Activity 4 - Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELN): **no changes**

Activity 5 - Data manager network: **reduced number of activities**

Staff concept and resources: To successfully address the broad topics covered by this measure ranging from further development of tools and their operation to user support and community building, different skillsets are needed. These will be delivered by service stewards (1 FTE divided across different provider organisations) and by software developers (1 FTE divided across different contributors). The community building aspects will be supported by the Task Area communication and coordination personnel.

TA3 Measure 3: Network of GFBio Data Centers

Lead: SNSB, **Co-Lead:** DSMZ

Contributors: All GFBio Data Centers

Activity 1 - The GFBio Data Center network: **no changes**

Activity 2 - Extending the GFBio Data Center network: **no changes**

Activity 3 - New technical solutions: **no changes**

Activity 4 - Curating, long term preserving and publishing of FAIR+ datasets: **no changes**

Activity 5 - NFDI4Biodiversity-adapted tools as services: **no changes**

Activity 6 - Blueprint workflows for major biological data types: **no changes**

Activity 7 - Concept and strategy for scientific data trustee organisations: **no changes**

Staff concept and resources: The extensive harmonisation efforts need experienced scientific data curators. These will also provide continuous curatorial and archival services

for new datasets (0.5 FTE each, [partially delayed start](#)) in each institution. In addition, this measure requires considerable coordination and communication effort (0.25 FTE coordinator position at the lead institution SNSB).

Deleted/merged: TA3 Measure 4: Service portfolio and lifecycle

~~Lead: GFBio, Co-Leads: GWDG, IPK~~

~~Contributor: BIBI~~

~~Activity 1 – Portfolio management~~

~~Activity 2 – Service monitoring program~~

~~Activity 3 – Identification of improvements~~

~~Activity 4 – Quality assurance~~

~~Activity 5 – Sustainability assessment~~

~~Activity 6 – Gap analysis~~

~~Activity 7 – Advancement of the NFDI4Biodiversity service catalog~~

This Measure was merged with TA3 M1; activities were partly integrated in TA3 M1.

Task Area 4

Research Data Commons (2create)

Lead: GFBio, **Co-Lead:** GWDG

Task Area 4 deals with the budget cuts by adapting the annual outputs and progress, and by reducing activities towards the objectives. No changes regarding the Milestones are made, and no Measures are dropped.

Milestones for Task Area 4 - *no changes*

Measuring progress towards SA4 (the specific aim of the Task Area): “A coherent data ecosystem in the cloud”

MTA	Project month	Milestone	Means of verification
4.1	18	Platform architecture and capabilities, including data mesh enhancements, are specified	Document describing RDC Platform is published
4.2	24	Data Product specification is available	Document describing content of a data product and requirements towards data providers is published
4.3	36	Processes for Data Product creation as well as data and service integration into the RDC Platform are defined	Documentation for creation of Data Products and for the usage of the RDC Platform are available

TA4 Measure 1: Data products

Lead: Uni Marburg, **Co-Lead:** UFZ

Contributors: GFBio, GWDG, JLU, SNSB, data domain experts from partner organisations

Activity 1 - Product design and implementation: *Initially, no more than 4 data products will be attempted, as a proof of principle*

Activity 2 - Data quality: *The data quality pipelines to be provided will be carefully selected to either (1) support the first data products, respectively the domain teams responsible for them, or (2) offer the most broad impact for our community. The number and complexity of the pipelines will therefore have to be reduced*

Activity 3 - Provisioning and scaling: **no changes possible**

Activity 4 - Agreement specification: **no changes possible**

Activity 5 - Search for novel data products and product marketing.

Roadmap for Data products (TA4 M1)		
	Roadmap 2030	Planned Approach
Data Products	Source-aligned and domain-aligned data products are accessible via a data catalogue.	We will establish domain teams to develop 4 data products.
Process for Product Development	A fully specified and standardised process for developing new data products is available.	We will create an NFDI-specific data product canvas and define a scalable process for potential domain teams.
Data Catalogue	A fully functional data catalogue is implemented with connectivity to GFBio Search and other established standardized APIs.	We will specify data catalog (e.g., DCAT)-based interfaces, conduct a requirements analysis, and select a catalogue solution that can be integrated at an early stage.
Data Quality	A comprehensive overview of data quality issues and conceptual solutions is available to support the full data product development lifecycle.	We will compile an inventory of existing data quality issues as they arise during the development process of concrete products and adopt already available data quality pipelines to address them
Data Pipelines	Based on TA4 tools, reusable and scalable data pipelines are available to support the creation of data products across domains.	Based on early development experiences, we will identify and document essential pipeline building blocks. These building blocks will be made available and documented in a way that allows their reuse beyond the initial exemplar data products.
Access Rights	A dedicated service for managing data agreements and defining access rights is available and integrated into product workflows.	We will conduct a field study of existing agreement and rights-management solutions, derive minimal requirements, and create a lightweight data-contract template needed for the first data products.

Roadmap for Data products (TA4 M1)		
	Roadmap 2030	Planned Approach
Product Marketing	Marketing content is available for roadshows, seminars, and demos at research venues. Community-driven pilots will demonstrate the scientific benefit of products, and reports will be published to promote data products.	We will continuously publish a Call4DataProducts in collaboration with TA1 and embed pilots directly into the data product canvas workflow. Marketing activities will focus on targeted demonstrations that show the added scientific value of the initial products.

Staff concept and resources: To implement this measure, we plan 1 FTE for a software developer/data scientist, complemented by in-kind coordination staff resources of the lead and co-lead organisations (UMR and UFZ). SNSB will contribute (0.25 FTE in TA3 M2) as a software developer/service steward capacities for coordinating and producing source-aligned data products from the GFBio Data Centers (project staff in Task Area 3 Measure 3). Additional project staff capacities for software development will be provided by GFBio (0.75 FTE). The GFBio Technical Lead and the coordinator at GWDG will coordinate the work of the domain teams.

TA4 Measure 2: Data and service integration

Lead: InfAI, **Co-Leads:** JLU, SNSB

Contributors: GFBio, UMR

Activity 1 - User-driven workflows: (Semantic) workflows implementation: initially one workflow will be implemented in collaboration with TA1 and TA2.

Activity 2 - RDC-internal workflows: Workflow implementation: connecting RDC services for the selected data products from TA4 measure 1. (LLM-support deleted.)

Activity 3 - Semantic descriptions: **no changes possible**

Activity 4 - Connectors: Define and implement external connectors to be used for the workflows from activity 1 and 2.

Activity 5 - Best practices and support: Focus on re-usable and self-teaching training materials and limit the offering of custom training.

Staff concept and resources: The measure is equipped with positions for software developers and service stewards at the lead and co-lead institutions InfAI (0.75 FTE for 2

years), SNSB (~~0.25 FTE~~ moved to TA3), JLU (0.3 FTE). Project staff employed by GFBio and UMR will contribute software development capacities with 0.5 FTE and 0.3 FTE (for 2 years), respectively.

TA4 Measure 3: Platform and core services

Lead: BIBI, **Co-lead:** JLU

Contributors: GFBio, GWDG, InfAI, JLU, UMR, GFBio Data Centers

Activity 1 - Platform operation: Maintain and evolve the overall RDC platform infrastructure, including all service areas of the roadmap (see below).

Activity 2 - Integration plan: **no changes**

Activity 3 - Development roadmap: **no changes**

Activity 4 - Technical onboarding: Support onboarding and integration of novel services into the platform, including those originating from Base4NFDI. This activity comprises introduction to concepts, provision of documentation, consultation and, if necessary, hands-on support.

Roadmap for RDC platform and core services (TA4 M3)		
Service Area	Roadmap 2030	Planned Approach
Authentication and Authorization (AAI)	RDC services support an authentication method that works for domain teams as well as users of other NFDI consortia.	The existing AcademicID-based GFBio SSO service will become "4BioLogin" and serve as the NFDI4Biodiversity Community AAI in the IAM4NFDI basic service.
Storage and Compute	Cloud-based storage and compute resources from at least two cloud centres are available for domain teams. This includes storage orchestration capabilities.	The de.NBI cloud centres at Bielefeld and Gießen as well as the GWDG cloud will provide storage and compute resources. The Aruna service will be extended to provide a unified interface to access multiple storage locations.
Workflow Execution	A service to manage and execute automated compute workflows is available for domain teams.	NFDI4Microbiota's CloWM service for Nextflow workflow management and execution will be adopted as an RDC service. An interface between the Aruna and CloWM services will be

Roadmap for RDC platform and core services (TA4 M3)		
Service Area	Roadmap 2030	Planned Approach
		developed together with NFDI4Microbiota. Additionally, the event system of Aruna will be available to trigger generic workflows that are not limited to a specific workflow engine.
Software-as-a-Service	Selected software services that are deemed essential for the operation of the RDC are integrated, operated and maintained. Base4NFDI services are preferred.	Appropriate catalogue services will undergo technical onboarding and continuous development to meet RDC policies.
Documentation	A central resource with documentation on how to use RDC platform services is available for TA3M1 and domain teams.	RDC platform documentation in the Knowledge Base will be continuously updated and extended.
Helpdesk	The Helpdesk service is continuously operated and has a well-established model of first- and second-level support, as part of the consortium's user support (TA1M5).	The technical personnel in Task Area 4 will contribute with frequently used responses for the first-level support.

Staff concept and resources: To implement the steps on the roadmap, measure lead BIBI is equipped with capacities for coordination, software development and service stewardship for the AAI solution (1 FTE) and provides in-kind technical support. Co-lead JLU receives funding for software development (0.7 FTE) and provides in-kind technical support. Capacities for software development are funded at InfAI (0.25 FTE for two years), UMR (0.2 FTE for two years) and GFBio (~~2-FTE~~ 1.25 FTE). GWDG will contribute DevOps Engineer expertise as in-kind. GFBio provides project staff capacities for service management (~~1-FTE~~ 0,5 FTE).

TA4 Measure 4: RDC governance

Lead: GWDG, **Co-Lead:** TBD

Contributors: GFBio, GFBio Data Centers, all consortium partners

Activity 1 - Coordination of flexfunds: **no changes possible**

Activity 2 - Policy framework: The policy framework will use appropriate, existing blueprints (e.g. EOSC) and adapt them to the needs of the consortium. The priority will be to set up a minimal, yet functioning framework that can be extended based on requirements and available resources.

Activity 3 - Alignment of activities: **no changes possible**

Activity 4 - NFDI-wide integration: The framework for service scalability will be developed based on continuous evaluation of the most pressing need. Enabling service providers to scale their offers with minimal efforts (optimal effort-benefit ratio) will be prioritized.

Staff concept and resources: The lead institution GWDG will be equipped with ~~0.75 FTE~~ 0.25 FTE for coordination, documentation, and dissemination of work and results. The GFBio Technical Manager will devote approximately 25% of his FTE for the establishment of policies and the alignment of efforts within the consortium. All other partners involved in this measure will contribute to policy definition and alignment with NFDI-wide activities through staff members active in other measures and their service stewards.

Task Area 5

Coordination, collaborative governance and sustainability (2coordinate)

Lead: UniBremen-MARUM, **Co-Leads:** GFBio, DSMZ, BIBI

In Task Area 5, the main strategies to deal with the budget cuts are the reduction of activities towards the objectives and, possibly, to adapt the annual output and progress. By contrast, no Milestones are changed or downsized, and no Measures are dropped or merged.

Milestones for Task Area 5 - *no changes*

Measuring progress towards SA5 (the specific aim of the Task Area): “Efficient and effective management and long-term strategy for sustainable services”

MTA	Project month	Milestone	Means of verification
5.1	12	Adapted governance structure implemented	Steering committee elected chairs SAB Phase II formed
5.2	36	Stress-test for reporting and coordination workflows	Interim report delivered
5.3	48	Transition from project governance to a long-term network governance is decided	Long-term strategy for the NFDI resource provider network in the biodiversity domain published

TA5 Measure 1: Project office

Lead: GFBio e.V., **Co-Lead:** UniBremen-MARUM

Contributors: Staff with TA coordination role

Activity 1 - Project monitoring and reporting: *no changes possible*

Activity 2 - Financial administration and management: *no changes possible*

Activity 3 - General management of the consortium: *no changes possible*

Activity 4 - Collaborative working environment: *Concentrate on access management for the internal wiki and virtual working environment, incl. maintenance and bug fixing; delegate content management*

Activity 5 - Committees and events: *Reduce number of Steering Committee meetings, simplify interactions with Strategic Advisory Board, reduce plenary meetings and decentralise their organisation*

Staff concept and resources: The Project office is led by the Executive director of GFBio (1 FTE) and is equipped with ~~4.5 FTE~~ 0,5 FTE for project coordination, management and reporting and 2 FTE administrative staff. Maintenance of the technical environment is provided in-kind by GFBio. UniBremen-MARUM will be responsible for the financial administration of the consortium and contribute administrative support through its legal and financial departments. GFBio will be the lead partner for project management, management of committees (Gremienbetreuung) and providing technical tools for collaboration. Task Area leads will associate their coordination staff to the Project office to ensure seamless workflows and support with the preparation of Steering committee meetings and events. On the level of NFDI, Project office leads and staff will participate in working groups on management, finance and reporting, as well as ~~any ad-hoc~~ selected activities decided by the NFDI.

TA5 Measure 2: Communications office

Lead: GFBio, **Co-Lead:** UGOE-SUB

Contributors: Staff with TA communication coordination role, volunteers

Activity 1 - Coordination of communication activities and dissemination

Activity 2 - Management of communication channels

Activity 3 - Representation of the consortium in key community events

Activity 4 - Support of communication measures and formats

Activity 5 - Project materials and merchandise

Activity 6 - Integrate with NFDI

The activities are intended to be carried out as outlined above; however, their frequency will be lower than originally planned (e.g., fewer attended events, fewer news campaigns). This implementation plan relies on a combined minimum contribution of 0.5 FTE from the TA1-4 coordinators. If this level of effort cannot be assured on a continuous basis, the Measure leads reserve the right to revisit and, if necessary, adjust the planned activities at a later stage.

Staff concept and resources: In the first funding period, resources for the implementation of communication measures were restricted to 1 FTE for public relations coordination plus an annual PR budget for professional support, as part of the central Project office. As dissemination of results picks up speed, the resources for PR need to be increased and structures aligned with other Task Areas. The Communications office will be led by the Public Relations Coordinator (1 FTE) who is responsible for the conceptual and editorial management of all mentioned dissemination measures. The co-lead will be a

Communication Manager (0.5 FTE) who supports the lead in all tasks as well as editorial work, event planning and committee work. The Task Area Leads associate staff with communication coordinator roles to the Communications office (~~0.25 FTE per TA 1-4; 1 FTE in total;~~ 0.1 FTE per TA; 0.5 FTE in total), who are familiar with ongoing work and current communications requirements. Their task will be to provide relevant information from their respective Task Areas, deliver content for the communication of results, and support dissemination activities. Given the limited staff resources, the frequency of newsblog articles and event participations will correlate with the number of volunteers. The Communications office will actively recruit volunteers and develop an attractive concept to motivate interested staff from partner organisations. An annual budget of ~~€ 30,000~~ € 20,000 (€ 10,000 in 2026) is foreseen for professional support with the development of project materials, communication campaigns and graphic design.

TA5 Measure 3: Integration with NFDI and sustainability

Lead: UniBremen-MARUM, **Co-Leads:** DSMZ, BIBI, GFBio

Contributors: All co-spokespersons

Activity 1 - Coordinate engagement in NFDI: **no changes**

Activity 2 - Cross-consortia collaborations: **Strategic focus 2025/2026: Biodata interest group**

Activity 3 - Base4NFDI: **Coordinate with Task Areas to prioritise engagements based on operational goals in 2026/2027, foster implementation of the prioritized basic services**

Activity 4 - Business models: **Concentrate on coordinated efforts in NFDI**

Activity 5 - Activities to communicate community needs: **Strategic focus 2025/2026: NFDI policy arena**

Activity 6 - Proposals **and exit strategy: Postpone activities until 2027, depending on decisions on sustainability of NFDI, monitor additional sustainable funding opportunities**

Staff concept and resources: The Measure will be led by the speaker and supported by all co-spokespersons. It will be equipped with 1 FTE for cross-community coordination ~~and 0.6 FTE for policy officers for professional and consistent communication of the consortium's needs~~. The consortium's Executive secretary will devote part of her time to support the activities in this Measure.

Appendix: Applicant, co-applicant and participating institutions

Applicant institution	Location
University Bremen	Bremen

Co-applicant institutions	Location
Freie Universität Berlin	Berlin
Friedrich Schiller University Jena	Jena
German Federation For Biological Data (GFBio e.V.)	Bremen
Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen	Göttingen
Justus Liebig University Giessen	Giessen
Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH	Braunschweig
Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research - IPK	Gatersleben
Philipps University Marburg	Marburg
Bavarian Natural History Collections (SNSB) Directorate General and Central Administration	Munich
Bielefeld University	Bielefeld
University of Kassel	Kassel

Participating institutions	Location
Alfred Wegener Institute – Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)	Bremerhaven
Arachnological Society (AraGes)	Putbus
Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (BfN) for Head office of the National Monitoring Centre for Biodiversity (NMZB)	Leipzig
Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH)	Hamburg
Federation of German Avifaunists (DDA)	Münster
German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure e.V. (de.NBI)	Heidelberg
German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research Halle-Jena-Leipzig (iDiv)	Halle-Jena-Leipzig
German Aerospace Center (DLR) for Rote Liste Zentrum (RLZ)	Bonn
Research Institute for Farm Animal Biology (FBN)	Dummerstorf
General Directorate of the Archives of the Bavarian State (GDA)	Munich
Georg-August-University Göttingen [with Göttingen State and University Library (SUB), Campus Institute Data Science (CIDAS)]	Göttingen

Association of German-speaking odonatologists (GdO)	Essen
German Ichthyological Society (GfI)	Bonn
Ecological Society of Germany, Austria and Switzerland (GfÖ)	Berlin
Goethe University Frankfurt	Frankfurt am Main
Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies gGmbH (HITS)	Heidelberg
Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ)	Leipzig
Hessian Agency for Nature Conservation, Environment and Geology (HLNUG)	Giessen
Institute for Applied Informatics association (InfAI) at Leipzig University	Leipzig
Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute, Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries	Braunschweig
Julius Kühn Institute (JKI) Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants	Kleinmachnow
State Office for Environmental Protection Saxony-Anhalt (LAU)	Halle (Saale)
Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB), Forschungsverbund Berlin e.V.	Berlin
Leibniz Institute for Regional Geography (IfL)	Leipzig
Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IÖR)	Dresden
Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research Warnemünde (IOW)	Rostock
Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change (LIB)	Bonn
Leibniz Centre for Tropical Research (ZMT)	Bremen
Max Planck Society for the Advancement of Science represented by Max Planck Institute of Biogeochemistry (MPI-BGC)	Munich, Jena
Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science (MfN)	Berlin
naturgucker.de non-profit registered cooperative	Northeim
Network Phytodiversity Germany (NetPhyD) c/o University of Rostock	Rostock
Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal and Nature Conservation Agency (NLWKN)	Hannover
RWTH Aachen University	Aachen
University of Kaiserslautern-Landau (RPTU)	Kaiserslautern
Senate Department for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action and the Environment	Berlin
Senckenberg - Leibniz Institution for Biodiversity and Earth System Research (SGN)	Frankfurt am Main
State Museum of Natural History Karlsruhe (SMNK)	Karlsruhe
Stuttgart State Museum of Natural History (SMNS)	Stuttgart

German Environmental Agency, National Centre for Environmental and Nature Conservation Information (UBA)	Dessau-Rosslau
Independent Institute for Environmental Issues (UfU)	Berlin
University of Duisburg-Essen	Essen
Leipzig University	Leipzig
University of Münster	Münster
University of Passau	Passau